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***Corresponding Author:**
T.S.Mahammed Basha

Assistant Professor,
Department of Electronics
and Communication
Engineering, JNTUA
College of Engineering,
Pulivendula, India

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Design and Performance Enhancement of Microstrip Patch Antenna Using Metamaterial Structures

**T.S.Mahammed Basha^{1*}, M.Siva Kumar², J. Nageswara Rao³,
K.Ravindra Reddy⁴, T.C.Sanjeewa Rayudu⁵**

^{1,2,3,4,5}Assistant Professor, Department of Electronics and
Communication Engineering, JNTUA College of
Engineering, Pulivendula, India

ABSTRACT

The project aims to design a microstrip patch antenna loaded with meta-material using HFSS. The main objective is to enhance the gain and bandwidth of the conventional microstrip patch antenna by more effectively loading the metamaterial. To reduce the size of the antenna, microstrip antenna technologies are miniaturised using high-permittivity dielectric substrates, shorting walls, and shorting pins. However, these methods have the disadvantage of narrow bandwidth and low gain. The new solution for this is to use electromagnetic metamaterials for antenna design. The use of metamaterials not only reduces size but can also improve other parameters, such as bandwidth and gain. A unit-cell Square SRR inserted along both sides of the feed achieves a maximum gain and a wide triple-band frequency range from 12 GHz to 18 GHz (Ku-Band). Ku band is mainly used in satellite communications and radar systems.

Keywords:- Square Patch (SP), Slots, metamaterial, SRR

INTRODUCTION

In wireless communication systems, microstrip patch antennas are widely employed due to their advantages such as low profile, lightweight, low cost, ease of fabrication, and simple design. The radiating patch is typically made from conductive materials like copper, gold, or nickel. The feeding mechanisms of microstrip patch antennas are generally categorized into two types: contacting and non-contacting methods. In the contacting type, RF power is directly fed through a microstrip line, while in the non-contacting type, electromagnetic coupling is used to transfer energy from the feed line to the radiating patch [2].

Despite their numerous benefits, microstrip patch antennas suffer from certain limitations, including narrow bandwidth, low gain, and limited directivity. However, for applications such as satellite communication, where high gain is essential, these challenges must be addressed. Various techniques have been reported in the literature to improve antenna gain, such as the use of Electromagnetic Band Gap (EBG) structures, Defected Ground Structures (DGS), Highly Reflective Surfaces (HRS), Artificial Magnetic Conductors (AMC), and Metamaterials [17].

This paper presents a method to enhance the gain and bandwidth of a conventional microstrip patch antenna by integrating metamaterials operating in the Ku band. Metamaterials are artificially engineered structures that exhibit electromagnetic properties not found in natural materials. In 1968, Veselago theoretically demonstrated that such materials could possess negative permittivity and negative permeability, distinguishing them from conventional materials [3]. Later, in 1999, Pendry introduced the concept of the Split

Ring Resonator (SRR), a fundamental building block of metamaterials. The SRR consists of two concentric metallic rings with splits on opposite sides, forming an LC resonator that can be excited by a time-varying magnetic field. The gaps between the rings act as capacitors, resulting in low radiation losses and a high-quality factor [4].

Over the years, several researchers have proposed innovative designs to improve antenna performance using metamaterials and structural modifications. Mandal et al. (2013) developed a high-gain, wideband patch antenna with two equal arms on a PTFE substrate, featuring an inverted U-shaped slot beneath the radiating patch. The design achieved an 86.79% impedance bandwidth (4.5–11.4 GHz) and a gain of 4.1 dBi, making it well-suited for wireless applications [7].

Attia et al. (2009) introduced a magnetic superstrate to enhance both gain and efficiency, achieving a 3.4 dB gain improvement and 17% higher efficiency at 2.2 GHz, with negligible impact on bandwidth [9]. Jieh (2003) designed a circularly polarized triangular microstrip antenna with triangular slots below the radiating patch, enhancing the gain by 3.3 dBi compared to conventional designs [10].

Similarly, Yingli et al. (2012) proposed a low refractive index metamaterial unit cell optimized to improve gain and beam focusing at 10 GHz, achieving 7.8 dBi with an effective refractive index near zero between 9.45 GHz and 10.7 GHz [8]. Saravanan et al. (2018) studied a phi-shaped metamaterial superstrate for a square patch antenna, resulting in a 7.94 dB gain at 2.4 GHz, validating the effectiveness of metamaterial-based enhancement [18].

**ANTENNA DESIGN
Conventional Square Patch Antenna**

Fig.1:-The geometrical design of the proposed conventional square patch antenna

The proposed antenna design starts with a square patch fed by a 50-ohm impedance microstrip line feed with a side length of

14.6mm. A square microstrip patch antenna is a form of antenna which consists of a square patch.

Table 1:-Dimensions of the patch antenna

Part	Dimension (mm)
Ground length	22
Ground width	25
Height of substrate	1.6
Patch length	14.6
Patch width	14.6
Feed width	1

The parametric analysis was conducted to finalise the substrate height. Iterations carried out were 1.8 mm and 1.6mm. By comparing the iterations of the substrate height, 1.6 mm is selected.

This section presents the parametric analysis and the evolution technique of the proposed antenna.

Square Patch Antenna With Plus Slot

Fig.2:-The geometrical design of the proposed square patch antenna with a plus slot

To improve antenna performance, a plus-shaped slot is incorporated into the rectangular patch antenna, with different dimensions.

Parametric analysis has been performed for different slot lengths and widths.

Table 2:-Dimensions of the plus slot

part	Dimension(mm)
Slot length	1
Slot width	3

From the obtained results, the antenna with a 1mm slot length and a 3mm slot width delivers an operational bandwidth of 580 MHz and a peak resonant frequency of 14.08 GHz.

SPLIT RING RESONATOR

Figure 3 illustrates the unit cell of the square SRR. To consider it as a metamaterial double negative property is verified from parametric values such as permittivity, permeability (μ) and refractive index (n)

Fig.3:-Design of square SRR

The square SRR has been analysed using the HFSS simulation tool, as per the specifications listed in the table. To calculate the S parameters, the unit cell is placed between two waveguide ports. Y plane is defined as Perfect Electric

Boundary (PEB) and the Z plane is defined as Perfect Magnetic Boundary (PMB). The SRR design is shown in Fig.4, to verify the double negative property of the unit cell MATLAB R2013b simulation tool is used to extract the values of S parameters.

Table 3:-Dimensions of Split Ring Resonator

Parts	Dimension (mm)
Outer Ring width	6.7
Outer Ring length	5
Inner ring width	4.7
Inner Ring length	3
Gap	0.5

Fig.4:- S Parameters of the metamaterial unit cell

The Fig.4 shows that S_{11} and S_{21} parameters have phase reversal at frequency of 10GHz. Hence the designed unit cell SRR is working as a metamaterial at its resonance frequency.

PROPOSED ANTENNA DESIGN WITH SRR

The SRR array is placed as a key building element between the patch and the ground plane, resonating at 10 GHz. The first requirement of the SRR array is the optimal spacing between its components. The performance of an array depends on the number of rings, the pattern of

arrangement and the orientation of the rings. The unit-cell SRR presented in section III is employed to design the Split Ring Resonator array, which can produce significant gain and bandwidth enhancement.

The proposed antenna is designed on a Roger RT-duroid 5880 substrate with a thickness of 1.6mm, a dielectric constant (ϵ_r) of 2.2, and a loss tangent of 0.0009. Each unit cell has an area of 4.84 mm². Different widths and lengths separate the SRR unit cells from each other according to their inter-element spacing.

Fig.5:-Design of a metamaterial-loaded microstrip patch antenna

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The simulated return loss of the proposed antenna is shown below.

Fig.6:-Return loss of the proposed antenna

A conventional square patch antenna with a plus slot offers multi-band operation at 12.35GHz and 14.05GHz, with bandwidths of 520MHz and 580MHz, a peak gain of 7.1dBi, and return losses of -15dB and -34dB. Square patch antenna

with a plus slot and a square SRR offers multi-band performance at 13.94GHz, 15.30GHz, and 16.26GHz, with bandwidths of 340MHz, 540MHz, and 2330MHz, and a peak gain of 18.8dBi and return losses of -17dB, -37dB, and -33dB.

The gain plot is represented in Figure 7

Fig.7:-Gain plot of the proposed antenna

Table 4:-Comparison with Designed antennas

Designed antenna	Resonant frequency (GHZ)	Bandwidth (MHz)	Gain(dBi)
Square patch antenna	12.18 13.19	420 510	17.7
Square patch antenna with plus slot	12.35 14.05	520 580	7.1
Antenna loaded with metamaterial	13.94 15.30 16.26	540 2330	18.8

Table 5:-Comparison with the Literature surveys

	Gain(d Bi)	Band width (MHz)
T. Sathiyapriya, V. Gurunathan and A. Shafeek "DESIGN OF METAMATERIAL INSPIRED HIGH GAIN PATCH ANTENNA".[1]	7.92	350
Journal of Engineering and applied science" SRR metamaterial- based broadband patch antenna for wireless communications" [2]	4.5	300
"Design of patch antennas based on metamaterials CSRRs" Nouri Keltourma LTC laboratory. [3]	5	30,320
Proposed antenna	18.8	340,540,2330

CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a square patch antenna with a plus slot, along with a square SRR, both designed for multi-band operation in the Ku band.

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